

Relationship between Pendant domination number, Graph Energy and Rank

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Abstract

In this paper, we establish several bounds that relate pendant domination number $\gamma_{pe}(G)$, graph energy G and rank of its incidence matrix. The motivation behind this work is to explore and establish meaningful connections between these graph parameters.

Keywords : Pendant Domination Number, Graph Energy, Rank of the incidence matrix.

1 Introduction

Berge's inspiration for the theory of domination came from a classical problem covering a chessboard with the smallest number of chess pieces. In particular, the problem was about finding the smallest number of pieces (like rooks, queens or knights) needed to cover or dominate all the squares on a chessboard. In graph theory, the domination problem involves determining the smallest set of vertices needed to ensure that every other vertex in the graph is adjacent to at least one vertex in this set is either part of this dominating set or is adjacent to a vertex in this set. The key idea is that a vertex is said to dominate another if it is either the same vertex or is connected to it via an edge. Domination theory has broad applications in Network Theory, Social Networks, Robotics and Surveillance and Mathematical Puzzles.

A dominating set $D \subseteq V$ is a subset of vertices such that every vertex in the graph is either in D or adjacent to at least one vertex in D . The cardinality of the smallest dominating set in G is called the domination number, denoted by $\gamma(G)$.

Let $G = (V, E)$ be a simple graph with the vertex set $V(G) = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_n\}$ and edge set $E(G)$. A subset $S \subseteq V$ is called a pendant dominating set of G if every vertex in $V - S$ is adjacent to at least one pendant vertex. A

pendant dominating set of minimum cardinality is called a minimum pendant dominating set, and its cardinality is referred to as the pendant domination number, denoted by $\gamma_{pe}(G)$.

Eigenvalues and eigenvectors play a crucial role in graph theory, providing deep insights into the structure and properties of graphs. By studying the eigenvalues of a graph's adjacency matrix or Laplacian matrix, one can uncover important features such as connectivity, centrality, stability, and other fundamental graph characteristics. Graph energy is a concept in spectral graph theory, given by the sum of the absolute values of the eigenvalues of the graph's adjacency matrix. It provides a measure of the graph's structure and is particularly useful in understanding the graph's connectivity and properties that are related to its spectral characteristics.

Since the pioneering work of Coulson [1], the area continues to attract interest in the general mathematical properties of the total π -electron energy ϵ as calculated within the framework of the Huckel Molecular Orbital (HMO) model. These studies have provided important insights into the relationship between energy and molecular structure. The properties of energy are discussed in detail in references [4], [6], and [7].

The rank of a matrix is a key concept in linear algebra, indicating the maximum number of linearly independent rows or columns in the matrix. It is determined by the non-zero rows in its row-reduced echelon form, which reflects the number of linearly independent rows or columns. The rank of a matrix is denoted as $rank(A)$ or $\rho(A)$. A matrix always represents a linear transformation between two vector spaces. The rank of a matrix reveals several properties of this transformation, and it is equal to the dimension of linear subspace spanned by its rows or columns.

In this paper, we establish several bounds that relate pendant domination number $\gamma_{pe}(G)$, graph energy G and rank of its incidence matrix. The motivation behind this work is to explore and establish meaningful connections between these graph parameters.

Theorem 1.1. *Let G be a complete graph without loops or multiple edges, $E_{pe}(G)$ be the graph energy, $I_{pe}(G)$ be the incidence matrix, $\rho(G) = rank(I_{pe}(G))$ represent the rank of $I_{pe}(G)$ and $\gamma_{pe}(G)$ denote the pendant domination number of G . Then*

$$\gamma_{pe}(G) = \left\lceil \frac{E_{pe}(G)}{rank(I_{pe}(G))} \right\rceil \text{ where } n \geq 3$$

Proof. The proof can be carried out in two ways:

- (a) Direct method (b) The mathematical induction method.
- (a) Direct method

Table 1: COMPLETE GRAPH

Graph	$\gamma_{pe}(G)$	$E_{pe}(G)$	$\rho(G)$	$\Delta(G)$	Eigenvalues of K_n
K_3	2	3.4641	2	2	0, 2.7321, -0.7321
K_4	2	5.1231	3	3	-1, 3.5616, -0.5616
K_5	2	6.8990	4	4	-1(2 times), 4.4495, -0.4495
K_6	2	8.7446	5	5	-1(3 times), 5.3733, -0.3733
K_7	2	10.6332	6	6	-1(4 times), 6.3166, -0.3166
K_8	2	12.5498	7	7	-1(5 times), 7.2749, -0.2749
K_9	2	14.4853	8	8	-1(6 times), 8.2426, -0.2426
K_{10}	2	16.4340	9	9	-1(7 times), 9.2170, -0.2170
\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots
K_n	2	$(n - 3) + \sqrt{n^2 - 2n + 9}$ where $n \geq 3$	$(n - 1)$	$(n - 1)$	$\lambda = -1$ with $(n - 3)$ multiplicity and $\lambda^2 - (n - 1)\lambda - 2$ with multiplicity one each.

W.K.T $\gamma_{pe}(K_n) = 2$
 Therefore $E_{pe}(G) = (n - 1) + \sqrt{n^2 - 2n + 9}$. From the above table we have,

$$\frac{E_{pe}(G)}{\text{rank}(I_{pe}(G))} = \frac{(n - 3) + \sqrt{n^2 - 2n + 9}}{(n - 1)} \leq 2$$

$$\left\lceil \frac{E_{pe}(G)}{\text{rank}(I_{pe}(G))} \right\rceil = 2 = \gamma_{pe}(K_n)$$

(b) Using the method of mathematical induction, it can be proven that $\left\lceil \frac{E_{pe}(G)}{\text{rank}(I_{pe}(G))} \right\rceil$

For K_3 we have, $\gamma_{pe}(K_3) = \left\lceil \frac{E_{pe}(K_3)}{\text{rank}(I_{pe}(K_3))} \right\rceil = \left\lceil \frac{3.4641}{2} \right\rceil = \left\lceil 1.7321 \right\rceil = 2$

For K_4 we have, $\gamma_{pe}(K_4) = \left\lceil \frac{E_{pe}(K_4)}{\text{rank}(I_{pe}(K_4))} \right\rceil = \left\lceil \frac{5.1231}{3} \right\rceil = \left\lceil 1.7077 \right\rceil = 2$

From the above, the result is valid for $n = k$

i.e., $\gamma_{pe}(G_k) = \left\lceil \frac{E_{pe}(G_k)}{\text{rank}(I_{pe}(G_k))} \right\rceil$

we will now prove that the result holds true for $n = k + 1$

$$\text{i.e., } \gamma_{pe}(G_{k+1}) = \left\lceil \frac{E_{pe}(G_{k+1})}{\text{rank}(I_{pe}(G_{k+1}))} \right\rceil$$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned} E_{pe}(G_k) &\leq E_{pe}(G_{k+1}) \\ \text{Rank}(I_{pe}(G_k)) &\leq \text{Rank}(I_{pe}(G_{k+1})) \end{aligned}$$

By inspection method we have,

$$2\text{Rank}(I_{pe}(G_{k+1})) > E_{pe}(G_{k+1})$$

Therefore, we conclude that the result is valid for $n = k + 1$ and hence the proof. \square

Theorem 1.2. *Let P_n be a path graph connected with no loops or multiple edges. Then*

$$\gamma_{pe}(P_n) = \left\lceil \frac{E_{pe}(P_n)}{\text{rank}(I_{pe}(P_n))} \right\rceil + [E_{pe}(P_n) - \text{rank}(I_{pe}(P_n))] \text{ where } n \geq 3$$

Proof. We verify the results for a few path graphs using Table 2.

Table 2: PATH GRAPH

Graph	$\gamma_{pe}(G)$	$E_{pe}(G)$	$\rho(G)$	$\Delta(G)$	Eigenvalues of P_n
P_3	2	3.6039	3	2	$\lambda = 2.2470, 0.5550, -0.8019$
P_4	2	4.8284	4	2	$\lambda = 1, -1, 2.4142, -0.4142$
P_5	3	6.5759	5	2	$\lambda = 1.6180, -0.6180, -1.1700, 2.4811, 0.6888$
P_6	3	7.5728	6	2	$\lambda = -0.2514, -0.7519, 0.8560, 1.9164, -1.2831, 2.5140$
P_7	3	8.8120	7	2	$\lambda = 0.2545, -0.5301, -0.8553, 1.1204, 2.0536, -1.5206, 2.4775$
P_8	4	10.4916	8	2	$\lambda = 1, -1, 0.1173, -0.6993, -1.5495, 1.4392, 2.2038, 2.24855$
P_9	4	11.5683	9	2	$\lambda = 0.2186, -0.3228, -0.7609, 1.0735, 1.7070, -1.1401, -1.5603, 2.2930, 2.4921$
\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots

Lemma 1.1. *Let G be a path graph or a cycle graph, then*

$$\gamma_{pe}(P_n) = \gamma_{pe}(C_n) = \begin{cases} \frac{n}{3} + 1, & \text{if } n \equiv 0(\text{mod } 3) \\ \lceil \frac{n}{3} \rceil, & \text{if } n \equiv 1(\text{mod } 3) \\ \lceil \frac{n}{3} \rceil + 1, & \text{if } n \equiv 2(\text{mod } 3) \end{cases}$$

‘ For P_3 we have,

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma_{pe}(P_3) &= \left\lceil \frac{E_{pe}(P_3)}{\text{rank}(I_{pe}(P_3))} \right\rceil + \lfloor E_{pe}(P_3) - \text{rank}(I_{pe}(P_3)) \rfloor \\ &= \left\lceil \frac{3.6039}{3} \right\rceil + \lfloor 3.6039 - 3 \rfloor \\ &= \lceil 1.2013 \rceil + \lfloor 0.6039 \rfloor \\ \therefore \gamma_{pe}(P_3) &= 2 \end{aligned}$$

For P_5 we have,

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma_{pe}(P_5) &= \left\lceil \frac{E_{pe}(P_5)}{\text{rank}(I_{pe}(P_5))} \right\rceil + \lfloor E_{pe}(P_5) - \text{rank}(I_{pe}(P_5)) \rfloor \\ &= \left\lceil \frac{6.5759}{5} \right\rceil + \lfloor 6.5759 - 5 \rfloor \\ &= \lceil 1.3152 \rceil + \lfloor 1.5759 \rfloor \\ \therefore \gamma_{pe}(P_5) &= 3 \end{aligned}$$

For P_8 we have,

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma_{pe}(P_8) &= \left\lceil \frac{E_{pe}(P_8)}{\text{rank}(I_{pe}(P_8))} \right\rceil + \lfloor E_{pe}(P_8) - \text{rank}(I_{pe}(P_8)) \rfloor \\ &= \left\lceil \frac{10.4916}{8} \right\rceil + \lfloor 10.4916 - 8 \rfloor \\ &= \lceil 1.3115 \rceil + \lfloor 2.4916 \rfloor \\ \therefore \gamma_{pe}(P_8) &= 4 \end{aligned}$$

To prove the result in general, we begin by considering a complete graph. By removing all the excess edges from a complete graph with n vertices, we obtain a path P_n . Consider the following equation:

$$E_{pe}(P_n) < E_{pe}(K_n) \text{ and } \text{rank}(I_{pe}(P_n)) \leq \text{rank}(I_{pe}(K_n))$$

From the above equation, we can conclude that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{E_{pe}(P_n)}{\text{rank}(I_{pe}(P_n))} &\leq \frac{E_{pe}(K_n)}{\text{rank}(I_{pe}(K_n))} \\ \implies \frac{E_{pe}(P_n)}{\text{rank}(I_{pe}(P_n))} &\leq \left\lceil \frac{E_{pe}(K_n)}{\text{rank}(I_{pe}(K_n))} \right\rceil \\ \frac{E_{pe}(P_n)}{\text{rank}(I_{pe}(P_n))} + k &= \left\lceil \frac{E_{pe}(K_n)}{\text{rank}(I_{pe}(K_n))} \right\rceil \end{aligned}$$

where k is a fixed constant, given by $k = \lfloor E_{pe}(K_n) - \text{rank}(I_{pe}(K_n)) \rfloor$

$$\therefore \left\lceil \frac{E_{pe}(K_n)}{\text{rank}(I_{pe}(K_n))} \right\rceil \leq \left\lceil \frac{E_{pe}(P_n)}{\text{rank}(I_{pe}(P_n))} \right\rceil + \lfloor E_{pe}(K_n) - \text{rank}(I_{pe}(K_n)) \rfloor$$

From Theorem 1, we can deduce that

$$\gamma_{pe}(P_n) = \left\lceil \frac{E_{pe}(P_n)}{\text{rank}(I_{pe}(P_n))} \right\rceil + \lfloor E_{pe}(P_n) - \text{rank}(I_{pe}(P_n)) \rfloor \text{ where } n \geq 3$$

□

Theorem 1.3. *Let C_n be a cycle graph which is connected with no loops or multiple edges. Then*

$$\gamma_{pe}(C_n) = \left\lceil \frac{E_{pe}(C_n)}{\text{rank}(I_{pe}(C_n))} \right\rceil + \lfloor E_{pe}(C_n) - \text{rank}(I_{pe}(C_n)) \rfloor - 1 \text{ where } n \geq 3$$

Proof. The above theorem can be proven in a manner similar to Theorem 2.

Table 3: CYCLE GRAPH

Graph	$\gamma_{pe}(G)$	$E_{pe}(G)$	$\rho(G)$	$\Delta(G)$	Eigenvalues of C_n
C_3	2	3.4642	2	2	$\lambda = 0, 2.7321, -0.7321$
C_4	2	5.2360	4	2	$\lambda = 2.6180, 0.3820, 0.6180, -1.6180$
C_5	3	7.4286	5	2	$\lambda = 1, -1, -1.2143, 2.6751, 1.5392$
C_6	3	8.3582	6	2	$\lambda = -0.2582, -0.8080, 1.8080, 1.2582, -1.6129, 2.6129$
C_7	3	8.9516	7	2	$\lambda = 0, 0, 2, \pm\sqrt{2}, 2.5616, -1.5616$
C_8	4	11.2126	8	2	$\lambda = 0.2528, -0.8931, 0.7472, 1.8391, -1.1453, -1.6069, 2.1453, 2.6069$
C_9	4	12.4898	9	2	$\lambda = 2, 0.6180, -1.6180, -0.3235, -0.8484, 0.9075, 2.1376, -1.4550, 2.5818$
\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots	\vdots

We verify the results for a few path graphs using Table 3.

For C_3 we have,

$$\begin{aligned}\gamma_{pe}(C_3) &= \left\lceil \frac{E_{pe}(C_3)}{\text{rank}(I_{pe}(C_3))} \right\rceil + \lfloor E_{pe}(C_3) - \text{rank}(I_{pe}(C_3)) \rfloor - 1 \\ &= \left\lceil \frac{3.4642}{2} \right\rceil + \lfloor 3.4642 - 2 \rfloor - 1 \\ &= \lceil 1.7321 \rceil + \lfloor 1.4642 \rfloor - 1 \\ \therefore \gamma_{pe}(C_3) &= 2\end{aligned}$$

For C_5 we have,

$$\begin{aligned}\gamma_{pe}(C_5) &= \left\lceil \frac{E_{pe}(C_5)}{\text{rank}(I_{pe}(C_5))} \right\rceil + \lfloor E_{pe}(C_5) - \text{rank}(I_{pe}(C_5)) \rfloor - 1 \\ &= \left\lceil \frac{7.4286}{5} \right\rceil + \lfloor 7.4286 - 5 \rfloor - 1 \\ &= \lceil 1.4857 \rceil + \lfloor 2.4286 \rfloor - 1 \\ \therefore \gamma_{pe}(C_5) &= 3\end{aligned}$$

For C_8 we have,

$$\begin{aligned}\gamma_{pe}(C_8) &= \left\lceil \frac{E_{pe}(C_8)}{\text{rank}(I_{pe}(C_8))} \right\rceil + \lfloor E_{pe}(C_8) - \text{rank}(I_{pe}(C_8)) \rfloor - 1 \\ &= \left\lceil \frac{11.2126}{8} \right\rceil + \lfloor 11.2126 - 8 \rfloor - 1 \\ &= \lceil 1.4020 \rceil + \lfloor 3.2156 \rfloor - 1 \\ \therefore \gamma_{pe}(C_8) &= 4\end{aligned}$$

To prove the above result in general, we consider a complete graph. By removing all the extra edges from a complete graph with n vertices, we obtain a cycle graph C_n . The proof is followed by the Theorem 1.2. \square

2 Conclusion

The theory of domination and the energy of graphs are both fundamental topics in graph theory with a wide range of applications in various fields such as network theory, computer science, chemistry, and even physics. In recent years many scholars are working in this area and also they are introducing new domination parameters. In this article we have initiated the relationship between pendant domination number, the energy of a graph and the rank of incidence matrix to complete graph, path and cycle graph.

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